

Wheat straw management for rice on a coarse-textured soil

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In the Punjab, rice - wheat is a common crop rotation. With combine harvesting, wheat residues are left in the field and either burned or incorporated before transplanting rice. We studied the effect of residue management on rice yield.

In 1985, straw from the wheat crop (about 7 t/ha) was removed from the field, incorporated, or burned. These treatments were compared with applying 12 t farmyard manure (FYM)/ha.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Soil was a nonsaline Tulewal loamy sand, Ustipsamment with pH 8.2, EC 0.22 mmho/cm, CEC 7.9 meq/ 100 g soil, and 0.20% organic C. Rice variety PR106 was fertilized with 120 kg N

and 26 kg P/ ha.

Incorporation of about 7 t wheat straw/ ha wheat straw and applying 12 t FYM/ ha had similar effects on yield and yield attributes of rice and on soil fertility parameters (see table). When wheat straw was removed, tillers/plant, N uptake, and organic C content of the soil were affected adversely. Burning the straw increased tiller density and grain yield over nonincorporation. It had no significant effect on organic C content and nutrients availability. □

Effect of wheat straw management and farmyard manure on yield, yield parameters, and nutrient uptake by rice and soil characteristics. Ludhiana, India, 1986.

Treatment	Rice yield (t/ha)		Nutrient uptake (kg/ha)			Plant height (cm)	Tillers/Plant	1,000-grain wt (g)	Soil organic C (%)	Available nutrients in the soil (kg/ha)		
	Grain	Straw	N	P	K					N ^a	P ^b	K ^c
Wheat straw removed	5.9	7.9	94	22	137	92	9.1	21.6	0.21	82	8.6	60
Wheat straw burned	6.5	7.8	99	23	135	94	10.3	20.6	0.22	76	8.4	73
Wheat straw incorporated	6.2	8.5	105	23	139	96	10.5	21.6	0.25	78	11.0	75
Farmyard manure	6.2	8.6	113	22	156	95	10.3	22.1	0.24	105	11.6	74
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.4	ns	9	ns	5	ns	1.2	ns	0.03	18	ns	ns

^a Hot KMnO₄ extractable. ^b Olsen's P. ^c Ammonium acetate extractable.

Rice hulls as organic fertilizer on transplanted rice

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The use of rice hulls as organic fertilizer on transplanted rice was evaluated during two wet (WS) and two dry seasons (DS), 1983-84. Rice hull was incorporated either just before the first plowing or before final harrowing at 0.5 and 1 t/ha. The 0.5 t/ha substituted for 1 bag 14-14-14 fertilizer and the 1 t/ha for 2 bags based on a recommended fertilizer rate of 90-28-28 kg NPK/ha, equivalent to 2.75 bags urea and 4 bags 14-14-14. The 14-14-14 was basal; urea was topdressed before panicle initiation (60 d after transplanting). Rice variety IR54 was used.

Yields with rice hulls were similar to yields with 90-28-28 kg NPK/ha (Table 1).

Table 1. Performance of IR54 with rice hull (RH) as fertilizer. ^a CLSU, Nueva Ecija, Philippines.

Treatment	Plant height at maturity (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Yield (t/ha)
Unfertilized	95	399	4.1
90-28-28 kg NPK/ha	98	428	5.6
0.5 t RH/ha	98	412	6.1
1 t RH/ha	101	432	5.8

^a Av of 3 replications within 4 seasons (2 WS, 2 DS).

Table 2. Costs and returns from RH as fertilizer.

Item	90-30-30 kg NPK/ha	1 t RH/ha	0.5 t RH/ha	Unfertilized
Gross income (\$)	1042.22	1114.81	1049.67	786.64
Cash expenses (\$)				
Labor	251.19	265.56	259.07	203.34
Material inputs	221.44	193.67	210.33	102.67
Overhead (\$)	171.82	170.35	171.61	153.52
Total expenses (\$)	644.45	629.58	641.02	459.52
Net income (\$)	397.77	513.14	442.15	309.12
Rate of return (%)	62	81	69	67

The highest cost of production and lowest rate of return were with 90-30-30 kg NPK/ha (Table 2). Rice hulls at

1 t/ha as replacement for 2 bags 14-14-14 gave the highest net income and rate of return. □